

Determination of Relative Stability of Citrato Complexes of Some Metal Ions by Paper Electrophoresis

H. G. MUKHERJEE and SAMIR KANTI DATTA

Department of Pure Chemistry, University College of Science, Calcutta-700 009

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Relative stability of citrato complexes of some transition metal ions, namely Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} have been done by paper electrophoresis using buffer solutions of citric acid and trisodium citrate as carrier electrolyte. Relative stabilities were determined by varying concentration or pH of the carrier electrolyte, keeping the ionic strength of the carrier electrolyte constant. From the migration data formation of anionic complexes of probable formula $(\text{MCit})^{2-}$ and $(\text{MCit})^{-}$, where $\text{M} = \text{Cu}^{2+}$, Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} and $\text{Cit} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_7/\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_7$, were suggested. The order of relative stability of the anionic complexes was found to be $\text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+}$ which supports the Irving and Williams order of stability of metal complexes with oxygen chelates.

STUDIES on relative stabilities of various metal complexes with tartaric acid, citric acid, tungstic acid by paper electrophoresis have been done by a few workers¹⁻³. Recently Mukherjee *et al.*⁴ studied relative stability of formate complexes of Fe^{3+} , Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} by paper electrophoresis. This work prompted us to study the relative stability of citrato complexes of Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} by paper electrophoresis.

Experimental

Migrants: 2% solution of $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were used as migrants.

Electrolytes: Stock solutions of trisodium citrate (0.1 M), citric acid (0.1 M) and sodium nitrate (2 M) were prepared as carrier electrolytes and were mixed in different proportions as shown in Tables 1-3. Sodium nitrate was used to maintain the desired ionic strength.

Procedure: Wieland and Fischer⁵ type horizontal electrophoretic apparatus was used. Whatman No. 1 (1 cm × 34 cm) paper strips were taken. One drop of each of 2% solution of Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} were electrophorized separately, using different carrier electrolytes mentioned as in Tables 1-3, under the potential difference of 220 V for 1 h. The electrophoretic movements are recorded in Tables 1-3. pH of the carrier electrolytes was measured in a Systronics 335 digital pH meter using glass electrode. Ionic strength of the carrier electrolytes was kept at 0.5.

Results and Discussion

It appears from Table 1 that Cu^{2+} and Co^{2+} migrate towards the anode when the concentration of sodium citrate is 0.01 M to 0.002 M, pH of the

carrier electrolyte is 7.45-7.20, and at constant ionic strength (0.5). Zn^{2+} migrates towards the anode only at high concentration (0.01-0.004 M) of sodium citrate when pH of the carrier electrolyte is 7.45 to 7.28 and ionic strength is constant. Ni^{2+} migrates towards the anode, when the concentration of sodium citrate is 0.01-0.003 M, pH of the carrier electrolyte is 7.45-7.22, and ionic strength remaining constant. But when the concentration of sodium citrate falls below 0.004 M, Zn^{2+} migrates towards the cathode as Zn^{2+} -citrato, when it falls below 0.003 M, Ni^{2+} migrates as Ni^{2+} -citrato towards the cathode, and below 0.002 M Co^{2+} migrates towards the cathode as Co^{2+} -citrato. But when the concentration of sodium citrate lies between 0.01 to 0.001 M, Cu^{2+} migrates towards the anode.

So, by paper electrophoretic study formation of anionic complexes can be predicted. From the resulting data, formation of anionic complexes of Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} of probable formula $(\text{CuCit})^{2-}$, $(\text{CoCit})^{2-}$, $(\text{NiCit})^{2-}$ and $(\text{ZnCit})^{2-}$, where $\text{Cit} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_7$, can be established. Bobtelsky *et al.*⁶⁻⁷ as well as Dey *et al.*⁸ separately suggested the above anionic citrato complexes of Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} at pH 6 to 8, which corroborates our study. The data in the Table 1 show that anionic Cu^{2+} -citrato complex is more stable than Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} -citrato complexes and the order of relative stability of the anionic citrato complexes is $\text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+}$.

Table 2 shows that Cu^{2+} behaves as an anionic complex throughout the concentration range (0.025-0.002 M) of sodium citrate, when pH (4.08) and ionic strength (0.5) of the carrier electrolyte are kept constant. Between the concentration of sodium citrate 0.025 to 0.005 M, Co^{2+} forms anionic complex, pH and ionic strength of carrier electrolyte are

TABLE 1

Sl. no.	Carrier electrolyte	Distance migrated in cm (+, anionic movement ; -, cationic movement)			
		Cu ²⁺	Co ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Zn ²⁺
1.	10 ml 0.1 M Na ₂ -citrate + 22 ml 2 M NaNO ₃ + 68 ml water 0.01 M (7.45)*	+3 to +3.7	+2.7 to +3.1	+2.4 to +3.0	+1.0 to +2.1
2.	5 ml 0.1 M Na ₂ -citrate + 23.5 ml 2 M NaNO ₃ + 71.5 ml water 0.005 M (7.32)*	+2.7 to +3.2	+2.0 to +2.6	+1.8 to +2.8	+0.7 to +1.8
3.	4 ml 0.1 M Na ₂ -citrate + 23.8 ml 2 M NaNO ₃ + 72.2 ml water 0.004 M (7.28)*	+2.5 to +3.1	+1.7 to +2.0	+1.5 to +2.6	+0.4 to +1.7
4.	3 ml 0.1 M Na ₂ -citrate + 24.1 ml 2 M NaNO ₃ + 72.9 ml water 0.003 M (7.22)*	+2.1 to +2.8	+1.4 to +1.8	+0.8 to +1.9	-0.3 to -1.7
5.	2 ml 0.1 M Na ₂ -citrate + 24.4 ml 2 M NaNO ₃ + 73.6 ml water 0.002 M (7.20)*	+2 to +2.5	+0.7 to +1.1	+0.3 to -2.1	Cationic
6.	1 ml 0.1 M Na ₂ -citrate + 24.7 ml 2 M NaNO ₃ + 74.3 ml water 0.001 M (7.08)*	+1 to +2	Cationic	Cationic	Cationic

* Na₂-citrate solution ; Concentration (pH).
pH (7.08-7.45), ionic strength (0.5) constant, Na₂-citrate variable.

TABLE 2

Sl. no.	Carrier electrolyte	Distance migrated in cm (+, anionic movement ; -, cationic movement)			
		Cu ²⁺	Co ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Zn ²⁺
1.	25 ml 0.1 M Na ₂ -citrate + 25 ml 0.1 M citric acid + 20 ml 2 M NaNO ₃ + 30 ml water (0.025 M)*	+3 to +3.1	+2.7 to +3.6	+2.4 to +3.1	+1.8 to +2.8
2.	10 ml 0.1 M Na ₂ -citrate + 10 ml 0.1 M citric acid + 23 ml 2 M NaNO ₃ + 57 ml water (0.01 M)*	+2.7 to +3.8	+2.4 to +3.1	+2 to +2.8	+0.8 to +1.7
3.	5 ml 0.1 M Na ₂ -citrate + 5 ml 0.1 M citric acid + 24 ml 2 M NaNO ₃ + 66 ml water (0.005 M)*	+2.1 to +3.5	+2.0 to +2.8	-1.2 to -2.3	-1 to -2.4
4.	4 ml 0.1 M Na ₂ -citrate + 4 ml 0.1 M citric acid + 24.2 ml 2 M NaNO ₃ + 67.8 ml water (0.004 M)*	+1.9 to +2.9	Cationic	Cationic	Cationic
5.	2 ml 0.1 M Na ₂ -citrate + 2 ml 0.1 M citric acid + 24.6 ml 2 M NaNO ₃ + 71.4 ml water (0.002 M)*	+1.3 to +2.2	Cationic	Cationic	Cationic

* Concentration of Na₂-citrate in solution.
pH (4.08) constant, ionic strength (0.5) constant, citrate variable.

TABLE 3

Sl. no.	Carrier electrolyte	Distance migrated in cm (+, anionic movement ; -, cationic movement)			
		Cu ²⁺	Co ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Zn ²⁺
1.	10 ml 0.05 M Na ₂ -citrate + 2 ml 0.05 M citric acid + 23.55 ml 2 M NaNO ₃ + 64.45 ml water (pH = 5.31)	+1.8 to +2.7	+1.6 to +2.4	+1.4 to +2.1	+1.3 to +2.1
2.	10 ml 0.05 M Na ₂ -citrate + 4 ml 0.05 M citric acid + 23.59 ml 2 M NaNO ₃ + 62.41 ml water (pH = 5.09)	+1.7 to +2.9	+1.3 to +2.4	+0.8 to +2.0	+0.5 to +2.0
3.	10 ml 0.05 M Na ₂ -citrate + 6 ml 0.05 M citric acid + 23.65 ml 2 M NaNO ₃ + 60.35 ml water (pH = 4.83)	+1.5 to +2.6	+0.7 to +1.4	+0.5 to +1.5	+0.2 to +1
4.	10 ml 0.05 M Na ₂ -citrate + 8 ml 0.05 M citric acid + 23.7 ml 2 M NaNO ₃ + 58.3 ml water (pH = 4.57)	+1.2 to +2.5	+0.3 to +1.3	Cationic	Cationic
5.	10 ml 0.05 M Na ₂ -citrate + 9 ml 0.05 M citric acid + 23.72 ml 2 M NaNO ₃ + 57.28 ml water (pH = 4.33)	+1.2 to +2.5	Cationic	Cationic	Cationic
6.	10 ml 0.05 M Na ₂ -citrate + 10 ml 0.05 M citric acid + 48 ml 2 M NaNO ₃ + 32 ml water (pH = 4.08)	+1 to +2.6	Cationic	Cationic	Cationic

Citrate concentration (0.005 M) constant. Ionic strength (0.5) constant, pH variable.

kept constant. Between the concentration of sodium citrate 0.025 to 0.01 M, both Ni²⁺ and Zn²⁺ form anionic complex, pH and ionic strength of the carrier electrolyte remaining the same. From the electrophoretic data, formation of anionic complexes of Cu²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Zn²⁺ of probable formula (CuCit)⁻, (CoCit)⁻, Ni(Cit)⁻, Zn(Cit)⁻, where Cit=C₆H₅O₇, as suggested by Bobtelsky *et al.*⁶⁻⁷ can be predicted. Hence, from the resulting data (Table 2), it can be concluded that the

order of relative stability of anionic citrate complexes is Cu²⁺ > Co²⁺ > Ni²⁺ ≈ Zn²⁺.

Table 3 indicates that Cu²⁺ forms anionic complex with the carrier electrolyte throughout the experiment (pH 4.08 to 5.31), when ionic strength of carrier electrolyte (0.5) and concentration of sodium citrate (0.005 M) are kept constant. Between pH 4.57-5.31, Co²⁺ forms anionic complex, ionic strength of carrier electrolyte and concentration of

sodium citrate are kept constant. Between pH 4.83 to 5.31, both Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} form anionic complexes, ionic strength of carrier electrolyte and concentration of sodium citrate are kept constant. Here also the anionic complex as $(\text{CuCit})^-$, $(\text{CoCit})^-$, $(\text{NiCit})^-$, $\text{Zn}(\text{Cit})^-$ as suggested by Bobtelsky^{6,7} can be predicted. So from the resulting data (Table 3) the order of relative stability of the anionic complexes is $\text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} \approx \text{Zn}^{2+}$.

From the three sets of experimental data it can be concluded that the order of relative stability of the anionic citrato complexes is $\text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+}$, thereby corroborating to some extent the Irving and William⁸ series of stability of metal complexes with oxygen chelates.

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